

TUBULIFERA APPLANATA. A NEW MYXOMYCETE SPECIES FROM EASTERN EUROPE AND NORTHERN ASIA

by

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Summary. D.V. LEONTYEV & K.A. FEFELOV (2009). *Tubulifera applanata*. A new myxomycete species from eastern Europe and northern Asia. *Bol. Soc. Micol. Madrid* 33: 115-127

Based on material collected in different regions of Russia and Ukraine, the new species *Tubulifera applanata* is described, differing from *T. arachnoidea* by the presence of ring-like ornamentations on the inner peridial surface, flat hexagonal tips of the sporocarps and salmon colour of young fructifications. Pseudoaethalia of *T. applanata* are substantially larger than those of *T. arachnoidea* and spores are significantly smaller, though spore sizes overlap. *T. applanata* differs from other 'sessile' *Tubulifera* species (*T. casparyi* and *T. dictyoderma*) by the structure of its columella-like strands and in the ultrastructure of the inner peridial surface. Annular embossments on peridium of *T. applanata* have much in common with 'rimmed craters', typical for inner peridial surface of *T. microsperma*. However, ornamentation of *T. applanata* is much lower in height, and the distance between annulations is much greater. The prismatic shape of the individual sporocarps and their flat, hexagonal tips are the most obvious peculiarities of *T. applanata*. As for similar 'flat' forms of *T. arachnoidea*, described earlier (*T. operculata* Pers., *Tubifera ferruginosa* var. *complanata* Meyl.), these, in view of their lilac tints and large fructifications, may be considered as early descriptions of *T. dictyoderma*. The above-mentioned diagnostic features are included in a modified identification key to the 'sessile' *Tubulifera* species.

Key words. flat tips of sporocarps, inner peridium ultrastructure, annular embossments, plasmodium colour, spore size.

Resumen. LEONTYEV D.V. & K.A. & FEFELOV (2009). *Tubulifera applanata*. Una nueva especie de mixomicete del este de Europa y norte de Asia. *Bol. Soc. Micol. Madrid* 33: 115-127

Una nueva especie *Tubulifera applanata* es descrita basada en material recolectado en diferentes regiones de Rusia y Ucrania. La nueva especie difiere de *T. arachnoidea* por la presencia de una ornamentación formada por anillos en la cara interna del peridio, extremos de los esporangios hexagonales y planos, y el color salmón en las fructificaciones jóvenes. Los pseudoetalias de *T. applanata* son claramente más grandes que los de *T. arachnoidea*, y las esporas son significativamente menores aunque los tamaños esporales se superponen. *T. applanata* difiere de otras especies sésiles del género *Tubulifera* (*T. casparyi* y *T. dictyoderma*) por la estructura de su falsa columela y la ultraestructura de la cara interna del peridio. La ornamentación como anillos del peridio de *T. applanata*, se parece a cráteres típico de la cara interna del peridio de *Tubifera microsperma*. Sin embargo la ornamentación de *T. applanata* es menos alta y la distancia entre ellas es mucho mayor. La forma del esporangio (prismático) y de la parte superior (plana y hexagonal) son las características más peculiares de *T. applanata*. En cuanto a las formas similares "planas" de *T. arachnoidea*, descritas anteriormente (*T. operculata* Pers., *Tubulifera ferruginosa* var. *complanata* Meyl.) a la

vista de los tintes liláceos y las grandes fructificaciones podrían ser consideradas como tempranas descripciones de *T. dictyoderma*. Las características diagnósticas incluidas más arriba, son incluidas en una clave de identificación modificada de las especies sesiles de *Tubulifera*.

Palabras clave. terminaciones planas del esporocarpo, ultraestructura del interior del peridio, anular hinchazones, color del plasmodio, tamaño esporal.

INTRODUCTION

The myxomycete *Tubulifera arachnoidea* was described by Nicolas Joseph von Jacquin in 1778. Independently, August Johann Batsch in 1786 described it under the name *Stemonitis ferruginosa*. Then, in 1792 Johann Friedrich Gmelin renamed *Stemonitis ferruginosa* Batsch as *Tubifera ferruginosa* (Batsch) J.F. Gmel. The latter name has been widely used in subsequent years. In 2001 Carlos Lado showed the priority of the name *Tubulifera arachnoidea* Jacq. (LADO, 2001).

Over the years, many authors have paid attention to the high degree of polymorphism of *T. arachnoidea*. Some of these authors (e.g., Christian Hendrick Persoon, Charles Meylan, Evžen Wichansky) described a number of forms and varieties of this species, including immature specimens [*Tubulina fragiformis* var. *coccinea* (Trentep.) Pers.], flat forms [*Tubulina fragiformis* var. *operculata* Pers., *Tubifera ferruginosa* var. *complanata* Meyl.] and forms with a well-developed hypothallus (*Tubifera ferruginosa* var. *albastipitata* Wichansky) (see LADO, 2001). However, none of these infraspecific taxa have been widely accepted. As a result, in modern identification handbooks rather problematic descriptions of *Tubulifera arachnoidea* are given. The size of the pseudoaethalium ranges from 5 mm up to 15 cm, spore diameter varies between 5 and 8 μm , and the colour of the plasmodium varies from transparent, white or yellow to pink and mulberry-red (NANNENGA-BREMEKAMP 1992; NOVOZHILOV 1993; ING 2001). Consideration of these descriptions leads one to assume that within the limits of *T. arachnoidea* a free continuum of the aforementioned parameters would exist. However, an analysis of our

collections has shown the opposite picture. The specimens of *T. arachnoidea* can be combined into distinct groups, demonstrating quite stable combinations of diagnostic features. Therefore, we concluded that *T. arachnoidea* is not a true species, but a species complex (LEONTYEV, FEFELOV, 2005). One of the most prominent taxa of this complex we describe here as a new species, called *Tubulifera applanata* with regard to its most noticeable feature – the flat tips of the individual sporocarps. The general appearance of this new species is quite similar to *T. arachnoidea* and could be considered to represent larger forms of it, if there were not be some additional distinguishing characters such as the unique ultrastructure of the inner peridial surface.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In our study, 61 *Tubulifera arachnoidea*-like specimens were included, 16 of which appeared to be the new species. In addition, 4 specimens of *T. dictyoderma* (Nann.-Bremek. & Loer.) Lado and 3 of *T. casparyi* (Rostaf.) Lado were used for comparison. The material examined was collected during 1997-2007 in various areas of Eurasia (Fig. 1). In Russia it was Ural Mountains (Sverdlovsk region: districts Nizhneserginsky, Revdinsky and Sysertsy; Komi Republic: Pechoro-Ylychsky Biosphere Reserve; Cheliabinsk region: Taganay Nature Park; Republic of Bushkiria: station '71 km'), Northern part of West-Siberian Lowland (Hanty-Mansiysky Autonomous Region, Nizhnevartovsky district), Altai Mountains (Altaysky Krai), Baikal Lake region (Irkutsk region) and Southern part of Russian Far East (Khabarovsk Krai); collector of all specimens K.A. Fefelov).

In the territory of Ukraine the material was collected in the East Left-Bank Forest-Steppe

Fig. 1 Area of investigation

1 Italy (Busana region). 2-4 Ukraine: 2. Roztochya forests; 3. Crimea Mountains; 4. East Forest-Steppe. 5-12 Russian Federation: 5. Republic of Bushkiria; 6. Cheliabinsk region; 7. Sverdlovsk region; 8. Komi Republic; 9. Northern part of West-Siberian Lowland; 10. Altai Mountains; 11. Baikal Lake region; 12. Southern part of Russian Far East.

The figure above the line indicates the number of *Tubulifera applanata* specimens; the figure under the line indicates the total number of *T. arachnoidea* and *T. applanata* collections.

(Kharkiv region, Gomolsha Forests National Nature Park), Crimea Mountains (Autonomous Republic of Crimea, Yalta Nature Reserve); Roztochya Forests (Lviv Region, Yavorivsky National Nature Park), collector of all specimens D.V. Leontyev. We also investigated 2 specimens from Busana region of Italy; collector A.Yu. Akulov. Material was deposited in the herbaria of the V.N. Karasin National University of Kharkiv (CWU) and the Institute of Plant and Animal Ecology RAS (SVER).

Examination of the specimens was carried out using light microscopy with oil immersion and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of native material. Pseudoaethalia were measured with a millimetre rule, and spore size (contour with ornamentation) was measured by ocular micrometer under oil immersion. Thirty spores were measured for each specimen to estimate the range of variation.

Methods of descriptive statistics, namely calculation of means, medians, quartiles, standard deviations, standard errors and confidence ellipsoids were used to describe the morphological variety of species. Quantitative data were compared using the criterion of Least Sufficient Difference (LSD-comparison, ZAX 1976). To analyze the type of distribution, a Distribution Fitting procedure was used, with subsequent estimation of distributions correspondence by the Chi-square method (LAPACH & *al.*, 2001). All calculations were executed using StatSoft Statistica 6.0, SigmaPlot 8.0 and Microsoft Excel 2003 software.

RESULTS

The new species, *Tubulifera applanata*, is characterized by its large, prostrate pseudoaethalia, prismatic sporocarps with flat, angular tips and dense, opaque peridium. Very character-

Fig. 2. *Tubulifera applanata* Leontyev & Fefelov

a. General view of pseudoaethalium; b. Pseudoaethalium surface from above, sporocarpal tips seen; c. Longitudinal section of pseudoaethalium fragment (schematically); d. Pseudoaethalium surface from above, sporocarps opened, columella-like strands visible; e. Spores under light microscope.

Fig. 3. Photo of *Tubulifera applanata* Leontyev & Fefelov

a. Young pseudoaethalium, general view; b-c. Mature pseudoaethalia; d-e. Intact sporocarpal tips from above; f. Opened sporocarps from above, columellae visible.

istic is the colour of young fructifications, which are salmon-coloured and never rose-pink. But the most important feature is the presence of annular embossments on the internal surface of the peridium. The diagnosis of the new species is provided below.

Tubulifera applanata Leontyev & Fefelov, sp. nov. (Figs 2-3).

(from *applanatus* (lat.) – flat)

Pseudoaethalia grandia, (12-)23-37(-73) mm longa, (7-)16.5-27.5(-38) mm lata, 4-6 mm alta, ovoidea vel irregularia, planopulvinata. *Sporangia* recta, claro prismatica, 5-6-marginalia. *Opercula sporangiorum* plana vel subconvexa, pentahexagona vel subrotunda, aequa forma, aequa altituda jacent. *Peridium* opacum, pallido-brunneum, muri sporangiorum laterales frequenter

oblique plicati. *Peridium interno* distanti circuli ornatum. *Structurae columelloideae* absunt vel sunt et non attingent apices sporangiorum, colourant similiter sporis. *Pseudocapillitium* absunt vel sunt et non multum, tenue, leniter ramosum, fibrosum. *Hypothallus* spongiosus. *Sporae* per saturam rufobrunneae, lucem brunneolae, 4.9-6 µm diam., reticulatae. *Plasmodium* salmonicolour, rufoso-cremicolour. In sylvis coniferosis, in rami et aculi dejecta, etiam in cortex et lignis leniter consumptis.

Pseudoaethalium large, (12-)23-37(-73) mm long, (7-)16.5-27.5(-38) mm wide, 4-6 mm in height, oval or irregular as seen from above, flat pulvinate. *Sporocarps* straight, clearly prismatic, 5-6-edged. *Tips* of sporocarps flat or slightly convex, 5-6-angular or more or less round, equal, arranged in one plane. *Peridium* opaque,

Fig. 4. Peridial ultrastructure in *Tubulifera* species
 a. *T. applanata* ($\times 4000$), ring-like ornamentation is indicated by arrow; b. *T. arachnoidea* ($\times 2000$); c. *T. dictyoderma* ($\times 4000$).

light brown, lateral walls of sporocarps often transversely plicate. *Internal surface of peridium* covered with annular embossments, quite distant from each other. *Columella-like strands* absent or not reaching the top of the sporocarp; coloured as a spore mass. *Pseudocapillitium* absent or scanty, appearing like slightly branched strings. *Hypothallus* spongy. *Spores* in mass rust-brown, brownish in transmitted light, 4.9-6 μm diam., reticulate. *Plasmodium* salmon, rusty-cream. *Ecology*: usually occurring in coniferous forests, on bark, litter and slightly decomposed wood

Holotypus: CWU-MR039, 14.07.2003, on the bark of fallen trunk of *Pinus sylvestris* L.; edge of pine forest (*Pinetum graminoso-herbosum*), Zadinetske forestry, Kharkiv region, Ukraine. Leg. D.V. Leontyev

Distribution. Investigated specimens were collected in (Fig. 1):

RUSSIA: Ural Mountains (Cheliabinsk region, Komi Republic, Sverdlovsk region); Southern

part of Russian Far East (Khabarovskiy Kray).

UKRAINE: East Forest-Steppe (Kharkiv region), Roztochya Forests (Lviv Region), Crimea Mountains (Autonomous Republic of Crimea).

It is worth noticing, that no specimens of *T. applanata* were found west of 25° E longitude. The authors are not familiar with any published pictures of similar specimens, found west from Ukraine. Therefore *T. applanata* thus appears to be a “continental” species, although additional investigations are necessary to prove it.

DISCUSSION

Peridium ultrastructure

In 1982, R.K. Nelson, R.W. Scheetz and C.J. Alexopoulos introduced a new diagnostic criterion into *Tubulifera* taxonomy – the type of inner peridial ornamentation. They found that in *T. microsperma* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Lado the inner surface has a very peculiar ornamentation.

tation, looking like “rimmed craters” – hollow cylindrical embossments on the internal surface of the peridium. In contrast, the similar species *T. arachnoidea* was shown to have an undulate and completely smooth surface of the peridium. Another investigated species, *T. casparyi* (Ros-taf.) Lado, appeared to have a granular inner surface of the peridium with scattered ‘craters’ (NELSON & *al.*, 1982).

A SEM-study of *Tubulifera applanata*, carried out by us, involved three specimens (CWU MR013, 037, 039). All of them demonstrated the unique combination of the abovementioned characteristics. Unlike *T. arachnoidea*, *T. applanata* constantly has an ornamentation with embossments, similar to the “rimmed craters” of *T. microsperma* but much lower, not looking like “craters” or “cups”, but like rings on the surface (Fig. 4a). These structures are seen also in light microscope, but not clearly (VAN HOOFF, personal communication).

The outer diameter of the peridial rings of *T. applanata* is 0.4-0.9 μm , similar to those in *T. microsperma*, which are 0.3-1 μm (NELSON & *al.*, 1982). However, the distance between the rings in *T. applanata* is much longer than in *T. microsperma*: usually it is 2-4 times longer than the diameter of ring (in *T. microsperma* the ‘rimmed craters’ are almost contiguous). In spite of the relative similarity of the peridial ultrastructure, *T. applanata* has nothing else in common with *T. microsperma*: it has no stem-like hypothallus like that typical of *T. microsperma* and its spores are never so small (see below).

The general appearance of the peridial rings in *T. applanata* is quite similar to those of *T. casparyi*, which are low and scattered on the granulate peridial surface (NELSON & *al.*, 1982). However, no granulations like those in *T. casparyi* are seen on the peridium of *T. applanata*.

Scanning electron microscopy of the peridium of *T. arachnoidea* and *T. dictyoderma* showed a pattern, quite different from that of *T. applanata*.

T. arachnoidea, as it was shown by NELSON & *al.*, has a smooth, undulate inner surface of the peridium (Fig. 4b). A single specimen of *T. dictyoderma* (SVER2510), was investigated which displayed a granular peridium with hemispherical, stellate or irregular, often aggregated granules 0.2-0.8 μm in diameter (Fig. 4c).

Tips of sporocarps

The oldest iconotype of *Tubulifera arachnoidea* (BATSCH 1786) and all classical pictures of the species (LISTER 1925; MARTIN & ALEX-OPULOS 1969; EMOTO 1977) show clusters of almost free cylindrical sporangia with convex, hemispheric or conical tips. All observed material of ‘typical’ *T. arachnoidea* has shown the same feature (Fig. 5c, g, h). In contrast, *Tubulifera applanata* has flat hexagonal tips and prismatic sporocarps (Fig. 3e). This character of our new species is the most obvious, but at the same time, the most questionable.

As far back as in 1799, C.H. Persoon described *Tubulina fragiformis* var. *operculata* Pers. (as *T. operculata*), which was defined by him as “*magna, subumbrina, primo variegata, tubules apice demum circumscissis*” (PERSOON 1799), which may be translated as “large, somewhat umber, at first variegate (?), apices of tubes are opened only by circles”. Inasmuch as ‘circles’ are probably flat tips of sporangia, could it be that C.H. Persoon just meant *T. applanata*? Apparently this is not, because the same feature is typical also of *T. dictyoderma*. Moreover, ‘subumbrine’ colour is very typical of the latter species (NEUBERT *et al.*, 1993) and not specific to *T. applanata*. So, it is likely that C.H. Persoon meant under ‘var. *operculata*’ the species *T. dictyoderma* which was described much later.

In 1931, Ch. Meylan described *Tubifera ferruginosa* var. *complanata*, and defined its distinctive features as the large size (up to 50 cm) and lilac-brown peridium (KOWALSKI, 1975). In 1975, Kowalski assumed, that the peridium colour mentioned by Meylan was a result of subjective perception and large sizes simply

Fig. 5. Photo of *Tubulifera arachnoidea*

a-b. Young pseudoaethalia, general view; c. Young sporocarpal tips; d. Pseudoaethalium on 'black' phase, sporocarpal tips; e. Pseudoaethalium on 'black' phase, general view; f. Mature pseudoaethalium, general view; g. Mature sporocarps from above, conical tips seem; h. Mature sporocarpal tips from the side

approached the maximum size of the species. As for the name ‘*complanata*’, Meylan unfortunately did not specify the reason for using the epithet. As a result, Kowalski assumed that it refers to general appearance of the pseudoaethalium: “*any pseudoaethalium would look flat if all its sporangia remained the same size and their number greatly increased*” (KOWALSKI, 1975). Based on this, Kowalski assumed that var. *complanata* does not represent a separate taxon. However, it is very likely that Meylan, using the name ‘*complanata*’, tried to point out that the flat surface of the pseudoaethalium is formed by the flat sporocarpal tips. If so, var. *complanata* is very similar to *T. applanata*. However, just like Person’s ‘*T. operculata*’, it is much more similar to *T. dictyoderma*, described in 1974 and, so, unfamiliar to Meylan and probably to Kowalski. As far as we know, only *T. dictyoderma* can form a pseudoaethalium of such a large size (see below) and only *T. dictyoderma* sometimes demonstrates a lilac (‘subumbrine’) tint of the peridium. In our opinion, *Tubifera ferruginosa* var. *complanata* Meylan is a synonym of *Tubulifera dictyoderma*, and not a variety of *Tubulifera arachnoidea*, as has been cited (LADO 2001). Consequently, this taxon cannot be considered to be a synonym of *T. applanata*.

Fructification size

Measurements show that pseudoaethalia of *T. applanata* are obviously larger than in *T. arachnoidea* (Tab. 1). Even when a fructification of *T. arachnoidea* is formed by confluence of several pseudoaethalia in a linear group, the width of such a group is only half of that of a separate

pseudoaethalium of *T. applanata*. However, size is always a very variable feature, especially in ‘collective’ fructifications like pseudoaethalia. We therefore analyzed this parameter statistically.

A distribution test has shown that the distribution of the size of pseudoaethalia in all investigated species (*T. applanata*, *T. arachnoidea*, *T. casparyi*, *T. dictyoderma*) demonstrates an unexpected significant deviation from Gauss distribution. The subsequent estimation disclosed, that the sizes of pseudoaethalia demonstrate the distribution, close to lognormal ($\chi^2=8.02$, $p=0.018$). Such distribution characterizes the parameters, for which there exists a precise bottom threshold (LAPACH & *al.* 2001). Such threshold can be determined by the amount of biomass, necessary for sporulation. As for the top border, it is not so strictly fixed.

The LSD-comparison confirmed that pseudoaethalia of *T. applanata* are significantly larger than those of *T. arachnoidea* ($p=0.032$), and smaller than in *T. dictyoderma* ($p<0.001$). In comparison with *T. dictyoderma*, *T. applanata* shows the same minimum but distinctly smaller maximum of pseudoaethalia size. Pseudoaethalia of *T. applanata* are also larger than those of *T. casparyi*, however LSD-comparison does not show a significant difference ($p=0.057$). All these facts are clearly seen from the scatterplot (Fig. 6).

Spore size

Spore size is used in the taxonomy of the *Tubu-*

Species	Specimens measured	Length (mm)				Width (mm)			
		Mean	Median	Quartiles	Range	Mean	Median	Quartiles	Range
<i>T. applanata</i>	16	32.40	31	23-37.25	12-73	22.7	23	16.5-27.5	7-38
<i>T. arachnoidea</i>	45	9.77	10	7-12.5	4-18	7.35	7	6-8	3-13
<i>T. casparyi</i>	3	12.86	9	6-12.5	5-39	10.14	7	5.5-8.5	4-32
<i>T. dictyoderma</i>	4	56.50	37	35.75-57.75	32-120	26.25	20	17.25-29	15-50

Table 1. Pseudoaethalium size in investigated specimens of *Tubulifera*

Fig. 6. Scatterplot for the pseudoaethalia size in *Tubulifera* species

lifer genus mainly to distinguish *T. microsperma* from other species, primarily from *T. arachnoidea*. All ‘sessile’ species of *Tubulifera* are usually described as having almost similar spores, 6-8 µm diam. (NANNENGA-BREMEKAMP 1992; NOVOZHILOV 1993; ING 2001). Precise spore measurements show that there exists some difference in spore dimensions of investigated species (Tab.2). The LSD-comparison shows significant differences among all investigated species, except for pair of *T. casparyi* and *T. dictyoderma* ($p = 0.055$). However, spore size of all species slightly overlaps, so this cannot be used as a good diagnostic feature (Fig.7).

It is worth noting, that spores of *T. applanata* appeared to be the smallest of all species investigated. They are somewhat smaller than in *T. arachnoidea* and significantly smaller than those

Fig. 7. Spore size range in *Tubulifera* species
Lines show standard deviations, boxes - standard errors of mean

of *T. casparyi* and *T. dictyoderma*. This detail is very interesting as a second feature (after peridial ornamentation), bringing *T. applanata* closer to *T. microsperma*. These facts indicate a necessity of detailed comparison between *T. applanata* and *T. microsperma*, which apparently are related species, although having quite different macro-morphology.

Species	Specimens measured	Spores measured for each specimen	Mean (µm)	SE	SD
<i>T. applanata</i>	16	30	5.451	0.045	0.548
<i>T. arachnoidea</i>	45	30	6.430	0.029	0.572
<i>T. casparyi</i>	3	30	7.183	0.582	0.539
<i>T. dictyoderma</i>	4	30	7.017	0.061	0.699

Table 2. Spore size in of investigated specimens of *Tubulifera*

Colour of immature fructifications

The colour characteristics are not widely accepted as diagnostic criteria in *Tubulifera* taxonomy. Mature fruitbodies of most species of the genus are rusty-brown. As for the colour of the plasmodium and young fructifications, it is described as very variable. For *T. arachnoidea* the plasmodium has been given as colourless, white, bright yellow, apricot, orange, pink, vermilion, salmon-colour, mulberry-red (LISTER 1925; NANNENGA-BREMEKAMP 1992; NOVOZHILOV 1993; ING 2001). Such diversity is quite unusual in Myxomycetes, and merits detailed consideration.

One obvious reason of this diversity is confusion between plasmodium and young fructification. It is likely that colours such as 'transparent' and 'white' characterize just a moving plasmodium, whereas different tints of pink and lilac colour are typical for young fructifications, which already have the shape of pseudoaethalium but still have not finished sporogenesis.

The second reason of colour diversity is identification difficulties. Typically, all the immature fructifications of *Tubulifera* are intuitively identified as *T. arachnoidea*, because other sessile species are quite rare and identifiable only in mature condition. If so, the colour of young pseudoaethalia can be much more species-dependent than previously reported.

All young specimens of true *T. arachnoidea* that we investigated have very characteristic carmine-pink fructifications (Fig. 5a, b) that can be lighter or darker but never salmon, lilac or purple. After sporogenesis is completed, the pseudoaethalium for a short time becomes almost black (Fig. 5b, e), and then dries to a brown colour (Fig. 5f-h).

In contrast, immature pseudoaethalia of *T.*

applanata are always salmon-coloured, lighter (flesh-coloured) when very young and darker while maturing (Fig. 3a). They lack a 'black' phase and 'wet' pseudoaethalia, which already contain spores, are brown (Fig. 3b). After drying, they become rusty-brown (Fig. 3c). The colour peculiarities of *T. arachnoidea* and *T. applanata* are very stable and can thus be used to good effect in species diagnostics.

Ecology

As has been indicated in the diagnosis, *T. applanata* usually occurs in coniferous forests, on bark, litter and slightly decomposed wood. Substrates for the species included *Pinus sylvestris* L. (Rostochia Forests, East Forest-Steppe of Ukraine, Sverdlovsk region), *Pinus pallasiana* D. Don (Crimean Peninsula), *Pinus sibirica* Du Tour (Komi Republic) and *Abies sibirica* Ledeb. (Chelyabinsk region). The most abundant collections were obtained from *P. sylvestris*, on which *T. applanata* fructified from Carpathians to Ural Mountains. In the type locality, the Gomolsha Forests National Nature Park, *T. applanata* also was found predominately on *P. sylvestris*, except for one specimen, collected the pine forest, but from the log of *Betula pendula* Roth. (Fig. 3b). Level of wood decomposition preferred by *T. applanata* is also very characteristic. It is usually found on recently fallen pine logs, with or without bark, but still quite solid. Three specimens were collected from ground litter, formed by fallen needles of *P. sylvestris*.

In contrast, *T. arachnoidea* was collected mostly in deciduous forests, on heavily decomposed wood of *Quercus robur* L., *Acer platanoides* L. and *Fraxinus excelsior* L., often covered by the moss (Fig. 5b, e). No specimens of *T. arachnoidea* were found on bark or leaf litter. So, the ecological characteristics also demonstrate the difference between *T. arachnoidea* and *T. applanata*.

KEY TO THE SPECIES OF *TUBULIFERA*

- 1 Pseudoaethalia sessile, pulvinate..... 2
- 1* Pseudoaethalia stipitate, on stalk or stem-like hypothallus
 *T. bombardata*, *T. dimorphotheca*, *T. microsperma*, *T. papillata* (not considered here).
- 2 Columella-like strands absent or sparsely present, but not attached to the peridium. Inner peridium surface not granular 3
- 2* Columella-like strands well developed, attached to the peridium. Inner peridium surface granular 4
- 3 Inner peridium surface smooth, undulate. Pseudoaethalia 7-12(-18) mm long, carmine-pink when young. Tips of sporocarps convex: conical or hemispherical. Usually in deciduous forests
□ *T. arachnoidea*
- 3* Inner peridium surface ornamented by annular ornamentations, 0.4-0.9 µm diam. Pseudoaethalia 2-4(-7) cm, salmon-coloured when young. Tips of sporocarps flat, angular. Usually in coniferous forests
□ *T. applanata*
- 4 Columella-like strands thick, dark-brown to black, usually connected with the peridium by perpendicular processes. Pseudoaethalia brown, yellowish-brown, 6-12 mm (to 4 cm) long. Tips of sporocarps hemispherical. *T. casparyi*
- 4* Columella-like strands thin, concolorous with the spore mass, with no perpendicular processes. Pseudoaethalia lilac-brown, 4-12 cm or more. Tips of sporocarps flat, angular
□ *T. dictyoderma*

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